

Table S4. Summary of autotrophic protist species analyzed in this study.

Dino: Dinoflagellates. Green: Green algae. Hapto: Haptophytes. Volume: cell volume (μm^3). T_{opt} : optimal growth temperature ($^{\circ}\text{C}$). E_{intra} : Intraspecific activation energy (eV) estimated by fixed-effect (OLS) model.

Group	Species	Habitat	Volume	Topt	Eintra
Diatom	Actinocyclus octonarius	Marine	293220	30	0.37
	Alexandrium fundyense				
Dino	strain BoF	Marine	11800	15	0.84
Diatom	Cyclotella cryptica	Marine	705	25	0.24
Diatom	Cyclotella meneghiniana	Freshwater	1820	25	0.54
Diatom	Cyclotella meneghiniana	Freshwater	1820	25	0.4
	Cylindrotheca closterium	Marine	80	22.5	0.77
	Dactyliosolen				
Diatom	fragilissimus	Marine	120166	18	0.47
Diatom	Detonula confervacea	Marine	2990	7	1.05
	Alexandrium fundyense				
Dino	strain MI	Marine	11800	15	1.05
Diatom	Detonula confervacea	Marine	2990	10	0.47
Diatom	Ditylum brightwellii	Marine	13900	12	1.13
Diatom	Ditylum brightwellii	Marine	17140	20	0.35
Diatom	Ditylum brightwellii	Marine	33400	26	0.39
	Dunaliella tertiolecta				
Green	strain CCAP 19/6B	Marine	227	20	0.57
Green	Dunaliella tertiolecta	Marine	183	28	0.62
Green	Dunaliella tertiolecta	Marine	227	25	0.92
	Emiliana huxleyi R				
Hapto	strain TQ26	Marine	36	20	0.92
	Emiliana huxleyi strain				
Hapto	G1779Ga	Marine	36	21	0.7
Dino	Alexandrium minutum	Marine	9610	20	0.99
	Emiliana huxleyi strain				
Hapto	B92/21	Marine	36	18	0.53
	Emiliana huxleyi strain				
Hapto	Van556	Marine	36	18	0.18
	Emiliana huxleyi strain				
Hapto	M181, Bigelow 1A1	Marine	36	24	0.82
Hapto	Emiliana huxleyi	Marine	36	18	0.75
	Emiliana huxleyi strain				
Hapto	S. Africa	Marine	36	24	0.68
	Emiliana huxleyi clone				
Hapto	M	Marine	36	20	0.9
Diatom	Eucampia zodiacus	Marine	20000	20	0.67
Green	Eudorina californica	Freshwater	4189	20	2.82
Diatom	Fragilaria barbararum	Marine	146	15	0.52
Diatom	Fragilaria crotonensis	Freshwater	204	25	0.46
Diatom	Fragilaria striatula	Marine	634	15	0.62

Diatom	Fragilariopsis cylindrus	Marine	24	5	0.1
Diatom	Fragilariopsis kerguelensis	Marine	825	4	0.41
Dino	Gambierdiscus toxicus	Marine	84100	29	1.44
Dino	Alexandrium ostenfeldii clone LF-37	Marine	22667	20.3	1.11
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica	Marine	48	25	0.75
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica strain AB1, CAWPOT	Marine	48	24	0.53
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica strain AB1, CAWPOT	Marine	48	20	0.51
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica var. typica strain A4725	Marine	48	27	0.53
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica var. typica strain A4727	Marine	48	27	0.61
Dino	Alexandrium tamarense clone GTMP	Marine	8840	20	0.75
Dino	Amphidinium klebsii	Marine	11100	27	1.6
Dino	Gymnodinium aureolum	Marine	3360	20	1
Dino	Gymnodinium catenatum strain GCCV-10	Marine	50400	29	0.32
Dino	Gymnodinium catenatum	Marine	40100	22.5	1
Dino	Gymnodinium corollarium clone GCTV-B4	Marine	5240	4	0.39
Dino	Gymnodinium isolate 581 (probably G. simplex)	Marine	567	27	0.5
Dino	Gymnodinium isolate 582 (probably G. simplex)	Marine	567	27	0.4
Dino	Gyrodinium instriatum	Marine	24800	25	1.01
Green	Haematococcus droebakensis	Freshwater	9140	20	0.3
Green	Haematococcus pluvialis	Freshwater	66	28	0.3
Diatom	Helicotheca tamesis	Marine	66700	25	1.43
Dino	Amphidinium sp.	Marine	1840	26	0.95
Dino	Heterocapsa rotundata	Marine	102	20	0.48
Dino	Heterocapsa triquetra	Marine	1690	16	0.54
Green	Heteromastix pyriformis	Marine	113	22	0.32
Hapto	Isochrysis galbana	Marine	81	24	0.09

Hapto	Isochrysis galbana clone T-ISO, NEPCC 601	Marine	59	25	0.96
Hapto	Isochrysis galbana clone T-ISO, NEPCC 601	Marine	59	27	0.69
Hapto	Isochrysis galbana	Marine	59	25	0.52
Hapto	Isochrysis galbana strain CCMP1323, Iso.	Marine	85	25	0.63
Hapto	Isochrysis sp. strain PS11	Marine	85	20	1.15
Diatom	Amphiprora paludosa	Marine	1930	25	0.63
Dino	Karenia brevis strain MAN	Marine	603	23	0.32
Dino	Karenia brevis strain APA	Marine	603	25	0.98
Dino	Karenia mikimotoi	Marine	8143	25	0.83
Dino	Karlodinium veneficum strain KT76E	Marine	808	20	0.54
Diatom	Lauderia annulata	Marine	18767	16	0.8
Dino	Leonella granifera	Marine	524	28	1.11
Dino	Leonella granifera	Marine	524	29	0.77
Diatom	Leptocylindricus danicus	Marine	1160	15	1.51
Diatom	Amphiprora sp.	Marine	1930	28	0.9
Diatom	Leptocylindrus danicus	Marine	1160	28	0.96
Green	Micromonas pusilla	Marine	1	20	0.21
Green	Micromonas sp. strain CCMP2099	Marine	8	6	0.94
Green	Nannochloris oculata	Marine	1	25	0.18
Green	Nannochloris sp.	Marine	10	30	0.84
Diatom	Navicula arenaria	Marine	4160	16	1.04
Diatom	Actinoptychus senarius	Marine	624114	30	0.48
Dino	Neoceratium furca	Marine	145000	20	1.1
Dino	Neoceratium fusus	Marine	158000	15	0.84
Dino	Neoceratium lineatum	Marine	53600	20	0.91
Dino	Neoceratium tripos	Marine	800000	20	0.1
Diatom	Nitzschia dissipata	Marine	243	25	0.7
Diatom	Nitzschia paleacea strain NT7	Marine	62	15	0.9
Diatom	Nitzschia seriata	Marine	601	10	0.35
Diatom	Asterionella formosa	Freshwater	2530	17	0.61
Diatom	Nitzschia sigma	Marine	3300	25	0.29
Diatom	Odontella mobiliensis	Marine	27700	27	1.11
Diatom	Asterionella formosa	Freshwater	156	20	0.35
Dino	Ostreopsis heptagona	Marine	200000	25	1.39

Dino	<i>Ostreopsis siamensis</i>	Marine	64700	25	1.92
Green	<i>Pandorina morum</i>	Freshwater	37153	16	0.58
Hapto	<i>Pavlova lutheri</i>	Marine	102	25	0.65
Green	<i>Pediastrum duplex</i>	Freshwater	4810	20	0.24
Diatom	<i>Asterionellopsis glacialis</i>	Marine	4440	17	0.27
Dino	<i>Peridinium sp.</i>	Marine	9490	18	0.78
Dino	<i>Pernambugia tuberosa</i> strain GeoB*74	Marine	8181	22	0.94
Hapto	<i>Phaeocystis antarctica</i> strain CCMP 1871	Marine	113	4	1.27
Hapto	<i>Phaeocystis globosa</i> strain CCMP 1528	Marine	65	20	3.2
Hapto	<i>Phaeocystis pouchetii</i>	Marine	80	15	0.91
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i> clone Pet Pd	Marine	9	23	0.38
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i> strain CCAP 1052/1A	Marine	128	21	0.49
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i>	Marine	132	20	0.34
Diatom	<i>Aulacoseira granulata</i>	Freshwater	352	30	0.34
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i>	Marine	80	20	0.7
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i>	Marine	120	20	0.56
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i>	Marine	128	15	0.35
Diatom	<i>Phaeodactylum</i> <i>tricornutum</i>	Marine	128	25	0.43
Green	<i>Picochlorum atomus</i>	Marine	8	20	1.22
Diatom	<i>Proboscia inermis</i>	Marine	99631	5	0.38
Diatom	<i>Biddulphia aurita</i>	Marine	12236	12	0.68
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum concavum</i>	Marine	68700	27	1.66
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum dentatum</i>	Marine	806	27	0.85
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum</i> <i>donghaiense</i>	Marine	806	20	1.31
Diatom	<i>Biddulphia regia</i>	Marine	791500	12	0.76
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum gracile</i>	Marine	2360	18	1.41
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum lima</i>	Marine	23600	27	1.97
Dino	<i>Prorocentrum</i> <i>mexicanum</i>	Marine	7137	27	2.34

Dino	Prorocentrum micans	Marine	16300	25	0.75
Dino	Prorocentrum minimum	Marine	2070	24.5	0.51
Dino	Prorocentrum minimum	Marine	1770	20	0.58
Hapto	Prymnesium patelliferum	Marine	592	30.1	0.84
Hapto	Prymnesium patelliferum	Marine	592	29.9	0.41
Diatom	Biddulphia sinensis	Marine	932250	30	0.26
Hapto	Prymnesium parvum f. patelliferum strain RHpat93	Marine	592	15	0.65
Diatom	Pseudo-nitzschia granii	Marine	425	14	0.41
Diatom	Pseudo-nitzschia multiseriata	Marine	1650	20	0.45
Diatom	Pseudo-nitzschia turgiduloides	Marine	282	3	1.48
Diatom	Pseudonitzschia pseudodelicatissima	Marine	298	25	0.9
Diatom	Pseudonitzschia seriata	Marine	1110	6	0.33
Dino	Pyrodinium bahamense var. compressum	Marine	21700	28.5	0.49
Hapto	Calcidiscus leptoporus strain N482-1	Marine	308	20	1.92
Diatom	Rhizosolenia fragillissimus	Marine	13100	18	0.47
Diatom	Rhizosolenia robusta	Marine	1200000	20	0.65
Diatom	Rhizosolenia setigera	Marine	875	12	0.83
Diatom	Rhizosolenia setigera	Marine	755	27	0.7
Green	Scenedesmus obliquus	Freshwater	179	30	0.4
Hapto	Calcidiscus leptoporus strain NS10-2	Marine	291	12	8.56
Green	Scenedesmus quadricauda	Freshwater	276	32	0.33
Dino	Scrippsiella trochoidea strain ScrpMxB	Marine	8470	16.5	0.33
Green	Selenastrum minutum	Freshwater	32	35	0.34
Diatom	Skeletonema ardens strain FDK003	Marine	167	35	0.39
Diatom	Skeletonema ardens strain FDK004	Marine	167	30	0.45
Diatom	Skeletonema ardens strain FDK005	Marine	167	35	0.55

Diatom	Skeletonema ardens strain FDK006	Marine	167	35	0.37
Diatom	Skeletonema ardens strain FDK007	Marine	167	35	0.38
Dino	Akashiwo sanguinea	Marine	132000	27	0.3
Dino	Ceratium furca	Marine	126000	24	1.26
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	258	25	0.82
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	258	15	1.2
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum clone SK6C	Marine	258	24	0.79
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum clone FHS 3	Marine	258	24.5	0.39
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	184	20	0.42
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum s.s. strain FDK009	Marine	258	25	0.62
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	161	25	0.5
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	213	20.1	0.4
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	376	25	0.64
Diatom	Skeletonema costatum	Marine	441	22	0.68
Diatom	Skeletonema japonicum	Marine	327	20	0.43
Diatom	Skeletonema japonicum	Marine	327	25	0.27
Diatom	Skeletonema japonicum	Marine	327	25	0.23
Diatom	Skeletonema japonicum strain FDK157	Marine	327	20	0.2
Diatom	Skeletonema japonicum strain FDK154	Marine	327	20	0.17
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoionohrnii complex strain FDK032	Marine	166	30	0.21
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoionohrnii complex	Marine	166	25	0.3
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoionohrnii complex	Marine	166	30	0.16
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoionohrnii complex	Marine	166	25	0.21
Dino	Ceratium furcoides	Freshwater	151000	20	1.29
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoionohrnii complex	Marine	166	30	0.15
Diatom	Skeletonema menzelii	Marine	57	35	0.47

Diatom	<i>Skeletonema menzeli</i>	Marine	57	30	0.49
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema menzeli</i>	Marine	57	25	0.62
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema menzeli</i>	Marine	57	30	0.39
	<i>Skeletonema</i>				
Diatom	<i>pseudocostatum</i>	Marine	198	30	0.36
	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>				
Diatom	clone fall	Marine	2500	31	0.61
	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>				
Diatom	clone spring	Marine	2500	31	0.91
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	25	1.63
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	31	1.02
Dino	<i>Ceratium fusus</i>	Marine	178000	26	1.1
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	25	0.3
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	25	0.4
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	30	0.3
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	30	0.31
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema tropicum</i>	Marine	2500	25	0.6
Diatom	<i>Chaetoceros calcitrans</i>	Marine	51	25	0.69
Diatom	<i>Stellarima microtrias</i>	Marine	53900	4	0.08
	<i>Stephanodiscus</i>				
Diatom	<i>hantzschii</i>	Freshwater	94	25	0.49
	<i>Stephanopyxis</i>				
Diatom	<i>palmeriana</i>	Marine	454000	20	0.24
Green	<i>Stichococcus cylindricus</i>	Marine	5	15	1.99
Diatom	<i>Synedra</i> sp.	Marine	47100	5	0.26
Green	<i>Tetraselmis</i> sp.	Marine	2570	22.5	0.83
	<i>Thalassionema</i>				
Diatom	<i>nitzschoides</i>	Marine	424	24	0.67
Diatom	<i>Thalassiosira allenii</i>	Marine	4320	20	0.21
	<i>Thalassiosira</i>				
Diatom	<i>curviseriata</i>	Marine	456	20	0.5
Diatom	<i>Thalassiosira decipiens</i>	Marine	5718	18	0.87
Diatom	<i>Thalassiosira eccentrica</i>	Marine	368000	16	1.13
Diatom	<i>Thalassiosira eccentrica</i>	Marine	59905	25	0.22
	<i>Thalassiosira</i>				
Diatom	<i>nordenskioldii</i>	Marine	7965	12	0.61
	<i>Thalassiosira</i>				
Diatom	<i>nordenskioldii</i>	Marine	5270	15	0.35
	<i>Thalassiosira</i>				
Diatom	<i>nordenskioldii</i> clone TN-2	Marine	2570	10	0.75
	<i>Thalassiosira</i>				
Diatom	<i>pseudonana</i>	Marine	91	24	1.63

Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	1.25
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	0.92
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	0.85
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	0.77
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	0.67
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	91	24	0.63
Diatom	Chaetoceros gracilis	Marine	77	20	0.81
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana clone 5A	Marine	91	20	0.95
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana	Marine	77	17.5	0.81
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1011	Marine	91	25	0.54
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1012	Marine	91	25	0.73
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1013	Marine	91	25	0.78
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1014	Marine	91	25	0.49
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1015	Marine	91	25	0.48
Diatom	Thalassiosira pseudonana strain CCMP1016	Marine	91	30	0.42
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula	Marine	42183	16	1.28
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula clone A8	Marine	40500	20	0.93
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula clone C8	Marine	40500	25	0.43
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula strain CCAP1085_21	Marine	40500	17	0.57

Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula strain CCMP3264	Marine	40500	17	0.72
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula strain GSO101	Marine	40500	17	0.45
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula strain JPNTR18	Marine	40500	17	0.34
Diatom	Thalassiosira weissflogii	Marine	615	20	0.8
Dino	Akashiwo sanguinea strain BWA	Marine	132000	25	0.3
Diatom	Chaetoceros simplex	Marine	168	25	0.61
Diatom	Thalassiosira weissflogii	Marine	2298	13	2.24
Diatom	Thalassiosira weissflogii	Marine	654	29	0.81
Diatom	Chaetoceros simplex	Marine	166	25	0.74
Hapto	Unidentified prymnesiophyte strain NT19	Marine	16	27	0.21
Green	Volvox aureus	Freshwater	5060000	24	0.27
Diatom	Chaetoceros sp.	Marine	64	20	0.46
Green	Ankistrodesmus falcatus CHL8	Freshwater	283	32.5	0.14
Green	Chlamydomonas reinhardtii CHL13	Freshwater	65	27.5	0.1
Green	Desmodesmus bicellularis CCAP276/14	Freshwater	385	35	0.33
Green	Desmodesmus quadricauda UTEX614	Freshwater	1571	32.5	0.59
Green	Monoraphidium minutum	Freshwater	196	27.5	0.37
Green	Scenedesmus acuminatus UTEX415	Freshwater	1753	27.5	0.36
Green	Scenedesmus maximus SAG39.81	Freshwater	424	35	0.67
Green	Scenedesmus obliquus SAG276/3a	Freshwater	172	27.5	0.05
Diatom	Chaetoceros sp. strain CS256	Marine	66	30	0.24
Green	Chlorella sp. strain MT-7	Freshwater	23	30	0.13
Green	Chlorella sp. strain MT-15	Freshwater	23	30	0.18
Green	Scenedesmus sp. LX1	Freshwater	276	25	0.53
Green	Scenedesmus quadricauda	Freshwater	276	33	0.34

Diatom	Chaetoceros sp.	Marine	2330	5.2	0.19
Diatom	Chaetoceros sp.	Marine	202	33	0.63
Green	Scenedesmus acutus Meyen	Freshwater	340	24	1.07
Green	Scenedesmus almeriensis	Freshwater	340	35	0.23
Diatom	Asterionellopsis glacialis	Marine	4440	31	0.71
Diatom	Asterionellopsis glacialis	Marine	4440	25	0.52
Dino	Calciodinellum albatrosianum Geob*26/5	Marine	126	28.6	0.45
Diatom	Chaetoceros deflandrei	Marine	NA	5	1.72
Diatom	Chaetoceros deflandrei	Marine	NA	7	0.79
Diatom	Chaetoceros didymus	Marine	2198	21	1.12
Diatom	Chaetoceros lorenzianus clone Bermuda	Marine	12660	30	0.49
Dino	Akashiwo sanguinea strain GBB	Marine	132000	25	0.3
Green	Chlamydomonas alpina	Freshwater	65	12.5	1.45
Diatom	Chaetoceros lorenzianus clone Bushehr	Marine	12660	21	1
Diatom	Chaetoceros lorenzianus clone Slope water	Marine	12660	27	0.45
Dino	Neoceratium fusus	Marine	49087	26	1.45
Diatom	Pseudo-nitzschia americana	Marine	18	25	1
Diatom	Rhizosolenia setigera	Marine	755	9	0.98
Diatom	Thalassionema nitzschioides	Marine	424	20.3	0.36
Green	Chlamydomonas globosa	Freshwater	144	18	0.48
Green	Chlamydomonas intermedia	Freshwater	65	18	0.43
Diatom	Skeletonema dohrnii	Marine	NA	22	0.51
Diatom	Skeletonema dohrnii	Marine	NA	22	0.24
Diatom	Skeletonema grethae	Marine	NA	22	-0.03
Diatom	Skeletonema grethae	Marine	NA	25	0.59
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	186	22	0.55
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	190	22	0.53
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	188	22	0.57
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	202	25	0.56

	Chlamydomonas				
Green	subcaudata	Freshwater	144	12.5	0.62
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	202	22	0.74
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	191	25	0.65
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	235	22	0.51
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	235	25	0.56
Diatom	Skeletonema marinoi	Marine	235	22	0.82
Diatom	Skeletonema menzelii	Marine	57	22	0.01
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	71	22	0.05
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	89	30	0.01
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	110	30	0.13
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	75	30	0.34
	Chlamydomonas UMACC				
Green	229	Marine	144	9	0.69
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	78	22	0.39
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	123	22	-0.5
	Skeletonema				
Diatom	pseudocostatum	Marine	77	4	2.7
Dino	Amphidinium carterae	Marine	877	30	0.44
Green	Dunaliella tertiolecta	Marine	295	30	0.24
Hapto	Emiliana huxleyi	Marine	63	25	1.62
Hapto	Gephyrocapsa oceanica	Marine	145	27	1.28
Green	Chlorella ellipsoidea	Marine	14	25	0.36
Green	Micromonas pusilla	Marine	1	30	0.56
Diatom	Nitzschia sp.	Marine	109	25	0.66
Green	Ostreococcus tauri	Marine	1	30	0.4
	Phaeodactylum				
Diatom	tricornutum	Marine	116	27	0.37
Green	Chlorella MFD1	Marine	23	25	0.2
	Thalassiosira				
Diatom	pseudonana	Marine	64	27	0.57
Dino	Thoracosphaera heimii	Marine	3897	25	0.38
Diatom	Chaetoceros sp.	Marine	1150	28	0.94
Diatom	Thalassiosira sp.	Marine	382	26	0.68
Diatom	Chaetoceros tenuissimus	Marine	524	30	0.39
Diatom	Synedra sp.	Marine	180	28	1.26

Green	<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Freshwater	38	39.2	0.54
Green	<i>Chlorella sorokiniana</i>	Freshwater	113	35	0.55
Green	<i>Chlorella</i> UMACC 237	Freshwater	14	20	0.19
Dino	<i>Akashiwo sanguinea</i> strain RMB	Marine	132000	25	0.42
Green	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Freshwater	11	30	0.39
Green	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Freshwater	11	30	0.24
Hapto	<i>Chrysochromulina</i> <i>polylepis</i> strain K	Marine	180	19	0.59
Hapto	<i>Chrysochromulina</i> <i>polylepis</i> strain B4	Marine	180	14	0.66
Hapto	<i>Chrysochromulina</i> <i>polylepis</i> strain B3	Marine	180	14	0.73
Hapto	<i>Coccolithus pelagicus</i> ssp. <i>braarudii</i>	Marine	1290	15	0.87
Dino	<i>Akashiwo sanguinea</i> strain YRB	Marine	132000	25	0.21
Hapto	<i>Coccolithus huxleyi</i>	Marine	18	20.6	1
Dino	<i>Cochlodinium</i> <i>polykrikoides</i>	Marine	24600	25	0.98
Dino	<i>Cochlodinium</i> <i>polykrikoides</i> strain 02B1	Marine	24600	27.5	1.01
Dino	<i>Cochlodinium</i> <i>polykrikoides</i> strain 02B2	Marine	24600	27.5	1.01
Dino	<i>Cochlodinium</i> <i>polykrikoides</i> strain 03H1	Marine	24600	27.5	0.8
Dino	<i>Cochlodinium</i> <i>polykrikoides</i> strain KG8- ND14	Marine	24600	27.5	0.83
Green	<i>Coelastrum microporum</i>	Freshwater	322	35	0.5
Diatom	<i>Conticribra guillardii</i> clone 7-15	Marine	981	15	0.84
Dino	<i>Coolia monotis</i>	Marine	16600	29	1.74
Diatom	<i>Corethron pennatum</i>	Marine	38000	4	0.41
Dino	<i>Alexandrium catenella</i>	Marine	9740	27	0.35
Diatom	<i>Coscinodiscus concinnus</i>	Marine	7601667	12	0.88
Diatom	<i>Coscinodiscus granii</i>	Marine	2204000	30	0.43
Diatom	<i>Coscinodiscus radiatus</i>	Marine	205000	30	0.38
Diatom	<i>Coscinodiscus</i> sp.	Marine	1620433	16	1.1
Dino	<i>Alexandrium catenella</i>	Marine	9740	14	0.97

	Fragilariopsis				
Diatom	kerquelenensis	Marine	1300	4	0.38
	Monoraphidium				
Green	minutum	Freshwater	21	35	0.34
Diatom	Stellarima microtrias	Marine	87995	4	0.09
Diatom	Eucampia zodiacus	Marine	5803	20	0.68
Green	Chlorella	Freshwater	103	26	1.28
Green	Golenkinia radiata	Freshwater	642	26	0.57
Dino	Biceratium furca	Marine	54615	24	1.42
	Stephanodiscus				
Diatom	hantzschii	Freshwater	669	25	0.53
Dino	Gyrodinium uncatenum	Marine	2010	28.5	0.67
Green	Pycnococcus provasolii	Marine	11	20	0.32
Green	Ankistrodesmus falcatus	Freshwater	34	35	0.1
Green	Volvox aureus	Freshwater	13	20	1.75
Diatom	Conticribra weissflogii	Marine	1705	29	0.86
Green	Volvox globator	Freshwater	13	20	1.24
Diatom	Stephanodiscus minutus	Freshwater	1313	20	0.16
Green	Scenedesmus	Freshwater	105	20	0.87
	Chlamydomonas				
Green	reinhardtii	Freshwater	155	25.5	0.65
Diatom	Entomoneis	Marine	2770	15	0.5
	Pseudo-nitzschia				
Diatom	multiseriis	Marine	1122	20	0.48
Diatom	Diatoma tenue	Freshwater	167	20	0.89
Diatom	Fragilaria capucina	Freshwater	293	20	0.14
Diatom	Fragilaria crotonensis	Freshwater	736	26	0.34
Diatom	Nitzschia holsatica	Freshwater	138	26	0.17
Diatom	Odontella aurita	Marine	21760	12	0.72
Diatom	Fragilaria crotonensis	Freshwater	736	20	0.4
	Stephanodiscus				
Diatom	hantzschii	Freshwater	669	20	0.23
Green	Botryococcus braunii	Freshwater	62	23	0.22
Diatom	Melosira italica	Freshwater	970	16	0.69
Diatom	Stephanodiscus astraea	Freshwater	9646	16	0.59
	Stephanodiscus				
Diatom	hantzschii	Freshwater	669	20	0.3
Green	Dunaliella tertiolecta	Marine	499	20	0.43
Dino	Biceratium furca	Marine	54615	20	1.17
Dino	Scripsiella trochoidea	Marine	938	16.5	0.33
Diatom	Asterionella formosa	Freshwater	344	20	1.14
Green	Chlorella	Freshwater	103	27	0.8
Green	Chlorella vulgaris	Freshwater	80	30	0.39

	Desmodesmus				
Green	quadricaudatus	Freshwater	153	25.5	0.73
Green	Haematococcus pluvialis	Freshwater	4814	28	0.31
	Monoraphidium				
Green	contortum	Freshwater	21	29	0.73
	Mucidosphaerium				
Green	pulchellum	Freshwater	25	25	1.02
Dino	Peridinium bipes	Freshwater	2010	20	0.45
Green	Raphidocelis subcapitata	Freshwater	22	24	0.33
Green	Acutodesmus obliquus	Freshwater	35	27.5	0.18
Dino	Alexandrium tamarense	Marine	1297	20	0.51
Diatom	Chaetoceros calcitrans	Marine	139	23	0.76
Diatom	Chaetoceros curvisetus	Marine	3023	22	0.27
Diatom	Chaetoceros simplex	Marine	344	20	0.57
Green	Chloroidea ellipsoideum	Marine	103	25	0.24
Diatom	Conticribra weissflogii	Marine	1705	12	2.97
Diatom	Coscinodiscus	Marine	5477	17	0.88
Diatom	Cylindrotheca closterium	Marine	208	23	0.41
Green	Dunaliella tertiolecta	Marine	499	32.5	0.75
Dino	Biceratium furca	Marine	54615	25	0.84
	Phaeodactylum				
Diatom	tricornutum	Marine	42	25	0.4
	Phaeodactylum				
Diatom	tricornutum	Marine	42	25	0.37
Diatom	Thalassiosira rotula	Marine	3768	18	0.58
Green	Chlorella vulgaris	Freshwater	80	25	0.6
Green	Chloroidea ellipsoideum	Freshwater	103	25	0.68
Green	Monoraphidium griffithii	Freshwater	113	32.5	0.14
	Acutodesmus				
Green	acuminatus	Freshwater	478	27.5	0.36
Green	Desmodesmus maximus	Freshwater	105	35	0.67
Green	Chlorella vulgaris	Freshwater	80	18	0.4
Green	Chlorella vulgaris	Freshwater	80	33	0.11
Green	Acutodesmus obliquus	Freshwater	35	25	0.36
	Desmodesmus				
Green	quadricaudatus	Freshwater	153	34	0.72
Green	Raphidocelis subcapitata	Freshwater	22	22	0.35
	Monoraphidium				
Green	contortum	Freshwater	21	10	0.58

Green	<i>Acutodesmus obliquus</i>	Freshwater	35	24	0.7
Green	<i>Chlorogonium</i>	Freshwater	61	40	0.15
Green	<i>Chlorella</i>	Freshwater	103	30	0.35
Green	<i>Micractinium pusillum</i>	Freshwater	40	35	0.59
	<i>Scenedesmus</i>				
Green	<i>almeriensis</i>	Freshwater	105	35	0.23
Green	<i>Acutodesmus obliquus</i>	Freshwater	100	30	0.35
	<i>Mucidosphaerium</i>				
Green	<i>pulchellum</i>	Freshwater	25	28	1.03
Diatom	<i>Fragilaria bidens</i>	Freshwater	280	20	0.59
Green	<i>Desmodesmus abundans</i>	Freshwater	11	35	0.56
Green	<i>Acutodesmus dimorphus</i>	Freshwater	208	35	0.37
Green	<i>Scenedesmus ecornis</i>	Freshwater	105	30	0.82
Green	<i>Pandorina morum</i>	Freshwater	368	15.5	0.58
Green	<i>Pleodorina californica</i>	Freshwater	223	20	2.58
Green	<i>Lobochlamys segnis</i>	Freshwater	155	18	0.42
Green	<i>Chlorella</i>	Marine	103	24	0.32
Diatom	<i>Conticribra weissflogii</i>	Marine	1705	20	0.81
	<i>Prorocentrum</i>				
Dino	<i>donghaiense</i>	Marine	10484	25	0.75
Green	<i>Oocystis</i>	Freshwater	123	25	1.18
Diatom	<i>Amphora</i>	Freshwater	480	35	0.21
Dino	<i>Peridinium bipes</i>	Freshwater	2010	20	1.05
Green	<i>Chlorella pyrenoidosa</i>	Freshwater	38	20	0.73
	<i>Chlamydomonas</i>				
Green	<i>acidophila</i>	Freshwater	155	20	0.78
Green	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Freshwater	4814	20	1.36
Green	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Freshwater	4814	25	0.47
Diatom	<i>Chaetoceros</i>	Marine	154	5	0.67
Green	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Freshwater	4814	20	0.37
Green	<i>Haematococcus pluvialis</i>	Freshwater	4814	15	0.9
Green	<i>Acutodesmus obliquus</i>	Freshwater	100	30	1.05
Green	<i>Nannochloris oceanica</i>	Marine	4	29.1	0.54
Green	<i>Chlorella vulgaris</i>	Freshwater	80	32.5	0.37
Green	<i>Nannochloris</i>	Marine	4	33	0.4
	<i>Desmodesmus</i>				
Green	<i>quadricaudatus</i>	Freshwater	153	33	0.35
Diatom	<i>Neocalyptrella robusta</i>	Marine	1336039	23	0.45
Diatom	<i>Odontella sinensis</i>	Marine	1000875	30	0.38
Diatom	<i>Skeletonema costatum</i>	Marine	808	25	1.42
Diatom	<i>Chaetoceros simplex</i>	Marine	344	25	0.68

Diatom	Fragilariopsis cylindrus	Marine	60	5	0.09
	Coscinodiscus				
Diatom	excentricus	Marine	80000	17	2.11
Green	Chlorella	Marine	103	25	0.2
